

Effects of Genotypes and Harvesting Time on Yield and Organoleptic Qualities of Pro-Vitamin A Cassava (*Manihot esculenta* Cratz) Garri

Ikeh A. O^{1*}., Ndaeyo N. U^{2.}., Akata, O. R^{3.}., Udoh E. I^{2.}., Akpan E. A^{3.} and Esang D. M^{2.}

¹Department of Crop Science, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo, Imo State, Nigeria

²Department of Crop Science, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Uyo, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

³Department of Crop Science, Faculty of Agriculture, Akwa Ibom State University, Obio Akpa Campus, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

*Corresponding author: angus.ikeh@uaes.edu.ng

Received: November 17, 2023; Accepted: May 4, 2023; Published: May 18, 2024

Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11213575

Abstract: The study was carried out at National Cereals Research Institute (NCRI), Uyo Out Station, Uyo, Akwa Ibom state, Nigeria, during 2012/2013 and 2013/ 2014 to evaluate the yield of pro-vitamin A cassava genotypes and organoleptic qualities of garri made from each genotype. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design, replicated thrice. The experimental treatments were ten Pro-vitamin A cassava genotypes (NR07/0246, NR07/0240, TMS1070134, NR07/0145, TMS01/1412, TMS01/1368, TMS01/1371, TMS1061635, TMS1070337, and TMS070593). The yield data and organoleptic attributes of garri generated through panelist were subjected to analysis of variance. Result showed that NR07/0240 produced significant larger storage root yield in overall; 34.29 and 34.13 tonnes/hectare in both cropping seasons. This was followed by 31.05 and 32.90 tonnes/hectare, respectively recorded in TMS01/1368. The least storage root yield; 21.11 and 21.95 tonnes/hectare in both cropping seasons was recorded in NR07/0145. NR07/0240 had significant storage root yield at 8 and 10 months harvesting while NR07/0246 and TMS01/1412 had significant storage root yield in 2012/2013 and 2013/ 2014 , respectively. NR07/0240 had significant higher garri yield; 11.77 and 11.51 t/ha in 2012/2013 and 2013/2014 cropping seasons. This was followed by 11.04 tonnes/hectare recorded in NR07/0246 in both cropping seasons. The least garri yield; 7.25 and 7.33 tonnes/hectare was obtained from TMS1061635. Comparing the overall sensory attributes of garri, NR07/0240 was rated best in appearance while TMS 070593 was the least in appearance. TMS 1061635 was the finest in texture while TMS 1070134 was the coarsest. NR07/0240 was best in sipping and dough quality.

Keywords: Cassava, Time of harvesting, Storage root, Garri yields and Organoleptic qualities

Introduction

Cassava (*Manihot esculenta* Cratz) is an important storage root crop in Nigeria. It is the major source of carbohydrates to many families in sub-Saharan Africa. According to Food and Agriculture (FAO) production data, the global cassava production in 2022 was estimated at 308 million tonnes. The total production from the continent of Africa was about 203 million tonnes (about 56% of global production). Asia produced 84 million tonnes while America was third in production rank, 26 million tonnes in 2022. In Africa, Nigeria alone produced about 60 million tonnes of cassava in 2022 (FAO, 2023).

Cassava is gradually gaining importance as an industrial crop in Africa and Asia. Except for carbohydrates, cassava is low in nutrient content when compared to other food crops. Cassava varieties previously grown in Nigeria were poor in nutritional qualities. The concentration of carotenoids, protein, zinc and iron are very low. As a result of in-depth research activities by the National Root Crops Research Institute (NRCRI) Umudike; Abia State, Nigeria, in collaboration with the International Institute for Tropical Agriculture (IITA) (Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria) and the International Centre for Tropical Agriculture (CIAT) (Colombia), yellow root flesh cassava

varieties were developed in Nigeria. The total carotenoid content of those genotypes ranged from 6.97 µg/g to 7.87 µg/g, signifying high carotene content when compared with white cassava flesh roots which are about 0.9 µg/g in most cases (Egesi *et al*, 2011). According to Inacio *et al*, (2024), the most common micronutrient deficiencies in cassava include vitamin A, iron (Fe), and zinc (Zn). The pro-vitamin A roots contain such micronutrients as carotenoids, iron, zinc and protein (Ezebuio *et al*, 2013). Vitamin A deficiency is more common in the sub-Saharan region of Africa where impoverished households lack sufficient resources to diversify their diet and purchase foodstuffs with high nutrients as supplements (Ezebuio *et al*, 2013). Such households mostly rely on carotenoids from plant sources such as the yellow flesh cassava roots, yellow maize, sorghum, sweet potato to meet vitamin A requirements of their bodies (Ikeh, 2017). Based on the daily and high consumption rate of cassava in west, central and east Africa, its bio-fortification becomes very necessary to enhance its micronutrient concentration. Incorporating essential micronutrients through breeding (bio-fortification) into this major and readily affordable staple crop could provide a cheap, quick, and strategic means of addressing micronutrient deficiency in most

food menu of poor and malnourished households within sub-Saharan region.

Vitamin A deficiency causes health challenges such as night blindness, Bitot's spot, corneal ulceration, Corneal Scars, blindness and premature deaths in children, and pregnant and lactating women. These health challenges is mostly within rural areas in west, central and east Africa and Latin America (Birner *et al*, 2007). The strategy seeks to take advantage of the consistent daily consumption of large amount of staple foods like cassava, sweet potatoes, wheat, yam, maize, beans, and rice in order to reach the targeted risk groups which includes; children and women in poor rural households. Vitamin A deficiency is a major cause of early childhood death and major risk for pregnant and lactating mothers. Vitamin A deficiency is a major nutritional challenge in low-income households more especially in sub-Saharan Africa and Latin America (Lucia *et al*, 2012).

Despite the fact that cassava is very low in nutritional value, particularly essential micronutrients, it still remains an important diets for over million 250 million people in Africa (Ademola *et al*, 2012).

The provision of adequate essential micronutrients is critical to health improvement of many households in Africa,

particularly in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). These essential micronutrients plays a significant role in metabolic activities and energy storage in the human body, more especially women during menstruation and pregnancy, and in children during normal growth and development (FAO, 2015).

Harvest plus is one of the programmes of the consultative group for International Agricultural Research (CGIAR) that was established in 2004 and the first recipient of funding for bio-fortification research by the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation. Since its establishment, harvest plus has been playing leading role in bio-fortification projects with a focus on three previously discussed micronutrients that pose a major health problem in Africa: Vitamin A, Iron, and Zinc. The project is targeted towards improving the nutritional content of seven staple food crops that include sweet potato, pearl millet, sorghum, beans, maize, wheat and cassava. The goal is improving health among young children and women in developing countries especially in Africa.

Yet, after the release of most promising pro-vitamin A cassava, there is some contradicting report on the exact time of harvesting these yellow roots. It has been noted that exact time of harvesting cassava

root depends on the variety, the rainfall, soil conditions, the temperature regime and the farmers need. According to (Ikeh, 2017), the most appropriate time to harvest cassava is when the roots must have accumulated sufficient amount of starch. Ikeh *et al*, (2013), note that optimum stage for cassava root harvest depends on varieties and environmental factors. IITA (1990) reported that late maturing cassava varieties are ready for harvest at 12 months after planting (MAP), while some early maturing cultivars are ready at 7 MAP months after planting. According to Udoh and Ndon (2016) and Ikeh, (2017), cassava is ready for harvest at 12 months when an appreciable amount of starch has accumulated on the tubers as harvesting too early will result in storage roots whose percentage as well as total quantity of starch is too low. On the other hand, harvesting too late produces tubers that are fibrous or woody, and increases the risk of tuber loss due to root rotting and pests attack (Onwueme and Sinha, 1991). In a field study conducted by IITA in 1990, with four cassava varieties: TMS60447, TMS53101, TMS37065 and TMS44086, the result showed that TMS44086 variety had the highest storage root yields at 15 MAP with decrease in yields at 21 MAP. Other studies have also shown that cassava varieties attain optimum fresh weight at 18 MAP (Ikeh et al,

2012; Bassey and Harry, 2013). Onwueme and Sinha (1991) reported that the local cassava cultivars grown in Africa are ready to harvest 12-15 MAP. Early-maturing varieties which are ready for harvest in 9 MAP have been introduced to many parts of Africa. With such cultivars, it is possible to plant and harvest the cassava within the same growing season. Many of these early-maturity varieties however suffer rapid root deterioration if left unharvested beyond the peak maturity time (Onwueme and Sinha, 1991). Udoh and Ndon, (2016), reported that most of the new cassava varieties are ready for harvest in 12-15 MAP but that storage roots of some of the early maturing types usually die after one year. Udoh and Ndon (2016) further stated that in some local cassava varieties (for example; *Obubit Okpo* and *Afia Okpo*; Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria local varieties of cassava) harvesting could be delayed up to two years and then yield become higher. In a recent study Ikeh (2017) stated that differences were observed in maturation of twenty four cassava genotypes while in some genotypes storage root yields at 8 MAP were not significantly different when compared with harvest at 12 MAP. In earlier study of Ikeh *et al*, (2013), some cassava cultivars like TMS97/0211, TMS98/0505, TMS98/0581 and local variety (*Obubit okpo*) produced significantly higher

storage root yields at 12 months compared to the yields at 9 months. IITA (1990); Bassey and Harry (2013); Ikeh (2017) and Ikeh *et al*, (2023a), reported that storage root yield is determined not only by the amount of dry matter produced, but also the pattern of partitioning of the dry matter to the different plant parts during growth. Ikeh *et al*, (2017) reported that time of harvesting had significant difference in processed products.

Materials and Methods

Experimental Site and Cropping History

This study was conducted at National Cereals Research Institute (NCRI) out station located at Owot Uta, Ibesikpo/Asutan Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria during 2012/2013 and 2013/2014 planting seasons. Owot Uta is situated between latitudes 04°30', 5°27' N, longitude 07°50' E, and 80°20' with altitude of 80 m above sea level (UCCDA, 1988). Owot Uta is located the humid tropical rainforest zone of South Eastern Nigeria and has an annual mean rainfall of 2500 mm and monthly sunshine of 3.14 hours with a mean annual temperature of 20°C. Owot Uta has a mean annual relative humidity of 70% and evaporation rate of 2.6 cm² (Peters *et al*, 1989). The rainfall pattern in Owot Uta is

bimodal. Rainfall usually starts in March and ends in November with a short period of relative moisture stress in August, traditionally referred to as “*August Break*” (Peters *et al*, 1989). The temperature of the area is generally high in the months of February through April (Peters *et al*, 1989). The experimental site was previously cropped to fluted pumpkin, rice and okra before it was fallowed for two years.

Experimental Design, Treatments and Plot Size

The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design and replicated three times. The pro-vitamin A cassava genotypes popularly known as yellow roots (NR07/0145, NR07/0246, NR07/0240, TMS 1070134, TMS 01/1412, TMS01/1368, TMS01/1371, TMS1061635, TMS1070337, TMS070593) was used as experimental treatments. The entire experimental area was 75 m x 20 m (1500 m²). Each plot was 6m x 6m (36 m²) with 10 plots in each replicate and total 30 plots in all. Spacing of 1m paths separated the plots and replications from each other, respectively.

Land Preparation and Agronomic Practices

The experimental site was ploughed, harrowed and ridged with a tractor and

marked out with measuring tapes, rope and pegs. Planting was done on crest of ridges, using 25cm stem cuttings long. Cutting was planted in an inclined position (45°) at 1.0 m x 0.8 m spacing. At 2 months after planting (MAP), NPK Mg (12:12:17:2) fertilizer was applied at 400kg/ha. The method of application used was ring. Manual weeding was carried out using a native weeding hoe at 1 and 3 MAP while slashing was done at 5 MAP. The cassava storage roots were harvested at the three sampling intervals of 8, 10 and 12 MAP.

Data Collection and Analysis

The following data were assessed. Ten plants were randomly tagged within each plot for data collection. The cassava storage root yields were determined with aid of top load weighing balance (Camry Mechanical Weighing Scale - 50kg made in China) in kilogram. The weight of harvested cassava storage roots was converted to tonnes per hectare. Harvested cassava storage roots at different time of harvesting were processed into garri at International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA) Processing Centre in Nung Udoe; Ibesikpo Asutan local government area of Akwa Ibom, Nigeria.

The garri samples from each treatment were poured into a stainless plate and presented to

12 panelists, drawn from the Staff and students of the Departments of Crop Science, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The panelists evaluated the following garri attributes: texture (feeling the samples between their fingers) on a six- point hedonic scale (1= very fine, 2= fine, 3= fairly fine, 4= fairly rough, 5= rough and 6 = very rough (IITA,1990). Appearance (by sight) on a five point hedonic scale (1= very good, 2 = good, 3 = fair, 4 = poor and 5 = very poor (Ihekoronye and Ngoddy, 1985). Preference of sipping garri in cool water and making of garri into “*eba*” with boiled water. The panelists indicated the degree of like or dislike on a five (5) point hedonic scale (1 = most preferred, 2 = preferred, 3 = fair, 4 = dislike and 5 = most disliked).

All the data generated from the experiment were subjected to analysis of variance using Genstat Discovering, 2012 version Model. Significant means were compared using least significant difference at 5% probability level.

Results and Discussion

Results

The number of storage roots per stand as influenced by cassava genotypes differed significantly ($p<0.05$) in both cropping

seasons irrespective of time of harvesting (Table 1). At 8 months, NR07/0240 genotype produced the highest number of storage roots per stand (15.33 and 15.17) in 2012/2013 and 2013/2014 cropping seasons, respectively. The least number of storage roots per stand (5.58 and 6.33) respectively, was obtained from NR 07/0145. The NR07/0240 genotype had 6-64 % and 8-58% higher number of storage roots than other genotypes at 8 months. At 10 months, NR07/0240 had the highest number of storage roots per stand (15.91 and 16.25) in both cropping seasons (Table 1). The least number of storage roots

per stand at 10 months harvesting (6.70 and 6.80) in both cropping seasons was recorded in NR 07/0145 genotype. At 10 months, NR07/0240 genotype had 5-56 % and 5-59 % higher number of storage roots more compared to the cassava genotypes. At 12 months, NR07/0240 genotype had the highest number of storage roots per plant (15.98 and 16.40) in both cropping seasons. The NR07/0145 genotype had the least number of storage roots (6.71 and 6.88) in both cropping seasons. NR07/0240 had 1-53% and 8-56% more storage roots per stand than other cassava genotypes.

Table 1 Number of storage roots per plant as influenced by cassava genotypes and Time of Harvesting

Cassava Genotypes	2012/2013				2013/2014			
	Months at harvest				Months at harvest			
	8	10	12	Mean	8	10	12	Mean
NR 07/0145	5.58	6.70	6.71	6.33	6.33	6.80	6.88	6.67
NR 07/0246	8.75	8.78	8.90	8.81	9.12	9.55	9.83	9.50
TMS 1070134	13.01	13.1	12.40	12.84	12.55	13.60	11.75	12.63
TMS 01/1412	14.75	14.8	14.13	14.56	14.99	15.22	15.45	15.22
TMS 07/0240	15.33	15.91	15.98	15.74	15.17	16.25	16.40	15.94
TMS 1061635	5.35	6.74	6.88	6.32	7.25	7.75	8.93	7.98
TMS 1070337	8.99	9.20	9.74	9.31	7.59	9.20	9.21	8.67
TMS 01/1368	12.81	13.97	14.07	13.62	13.40	13.48	13.40	13.43
TMS 01/1371	9.25	9.33	9.34	9.31	10.20	10.41	10.88	10.50
TMS 070593	8.28	8.55	9.18	8.67	8.59	8.75	8.76	8.70
LSD(p<0.05)	3.12	3.50	2.99	3.13	2.60	3.77	3.28	3.20

The cassava storage root yield as influenced by genotypes at different harvesting period varied significantly ($p < 0.05$) in both cropping seasons (Table 2). At 8 months harvesting, cassava storage root yield ranged from 12.34 t/ha in NR07/0145 to 34.41t/ha in NR 07/0240 genotype in 2012/2013 cropping season, and 13.92t/ha to 34.12t/ha, respectively in 2013/2013 cropping season. At 10 months harvesting, NR 07/0246 had the highest storage root yield 35.34 and 34.65 t/ha)

in 2012/2013 and 2013/2014 cropping seasons respectively. NR07/0145 had the least storage yield in 2012/2013 (24.49 t/ha) and 2013/2014 (24.43 t/ha) cropping seasons. At 12 months harvesting, cassava storage root yield ranged from 26.52 t/h NR07/0145 and 34.99 t/ha in TMS01/1412 in 2012/2013 cropping season and between 27.49 t/ha in NR07/0145 and 35.01 t/ha in NR07/0145 in second seasons.

Table 2 Cassava storage root yield (t/ha) as influenced by genotypes at different time of harvesting

Cassava genotypes	2012/2013				2013/2014			
	Months at harvest				Months at harvest			
	8	10	12	Mean	8	10	12	Mean
NR 07/0145	12.34	24.49	26.52	21.11	13.92	24.43	27.49	21.95
NR 07/0246	20.20	35.34	35.40	30.31	29.40	34.65	34.70	32.92
TMS 1070134	22.45	22.60	22.62	22.56	24.14	26.70	28.40	26.41
TMS 01/1412	30.48	31.49	34.99	32.32	29.85	30.01	35.01	31.62
NR 07/0240	34.41	34.48	33.99	34.29	34.12	34.18	34.10	34.13
TMS 1061635	25.36	25.45	25.74	25.52	26.08	26.25	26.28	26.20
TMS 1070337	29.25	31.09	31.02	30.45	30.40	31.02	31.04	30.82
TMS 01/1368	31.13	31.18	30.85	31.05	32.66	33.01	33.03	32.90
TMS 01/1371	28.55	28.59	28.60	28.58	27.91	28.08	28.17	28.05
TMS 070593	30.10	30.12	29.40	29.87	30.11	30.18	30.34	30.21
LSD(p<0.05)	4.31	3.46	2.68	2.81	3.90	3.71	3.57	3.45

Garri yield as influenced by cassava genotypes differed significantly among the cassava genotypes ($p<0.05$) in both cropping seasons irrespective of harvesting period (Table 3). NR07/0240 genotype had the highest garri yield (11.65 t/ha) and (11.25 t/ha) in 2012/2013 and 2013/2014 cropping seasons respectively. This was followed by 10.69 and 10.40 t/ha recorded in NR07/0246 in both cropping seasons. The least garri yield at 8 months harvesting; (4.94t/ha) and (4.82 t/ha) in both cropping seasons respectively was recorded from NR07/0145. At 10 months

harvesting, the garri yield also varied significantly in both cropping seasons. NR07/0240 had the highest garri yield of 11.70 and 11.60 t/ha in both cropping seasons. NR07/0246 produced 11.20 and 11.30 t/ha garri yield in 2012/2013 and 2013/2014 cropping seasons, respectively. At 12 months harvesting, TMS01/1412 had the highest garri yield (12.08 t/ha) and (12.11t/ha) in 2012/2013 and 2013/2014 cropping seasons, respectively. At 12 MAP harvesting, TMS1061635 had the least garri yield of 7.40 and 7.39 t/ha in both cropping seasons.

Table 3 Garri yield (t/ha) as influenced by cassava genotypes at different time of harvesting

Cassava genotypes	2012/2013				2013/2014			
	Months after planting				Months after planting			
	8	10	12	Mean	8	10	12	Mean
NR 07/0145	4.95	6.21	7.81	6.32	4.82	7.55	8.98	7.12
NR 07/0246	10.69	11.20	11.24	11.04	10.40	11.33	11.39	11.04
TMS 1070134	8.33	8.39	8.55	8.42	8.41	8.54	8.60	8.52
TMS 01/1412	8.14	8.18	8.22	8.18	7.97	8.07	8.19	8.08
NR 07/0240	11.65	11.78	11.89	11.77	11.25	11.60	11.68	11.51
TMS 1061635	7.15	7.20	7.40	7.25	7.28	7.33	7.39	7.33
TMS 1070337	8.44	8.98	8.85	8.76	7.95	8.84	8.90	8.56
TMS 01/1368	10.38	10.47	10.13	10.33	10.40	10.50	10.41	10.44
TMS 01/1371	7.81	7.90	8.92	8.21	7.75	8.91	8.98	8.55
TMS 070593	9.75	9.80	9.15	9.57	9.48	9.70	9.55	9.58
LSD($p<0.05$)	2.48	2.51	2.66	2.71	2.17	2.30	2.41	2.55

The appearance of garri as influenced by cassava genotypes showed significant difference ($p<0.05$) in all the harvesting periods (Table 4) on 5-point hedonic scale. Panelists rated NR 07/0246 as the best in appearance at 8 months in 2012/2013 (1.01) and 2013/2014 (1.00) cropping seasons,

respectively. The least rated was garri from TMS 01/1371 genotype in 2012/2013(4.50) and 2013/2014(4.90) cropping season, respectively. At 10 months, the best in appearance (1.08 and 1.05) respectively was from garri from NR 07/0240 genotype whereas the least in appearance (3.67 and

3.93 on 5-point hedonic scale) in both cropping seasons was garri from TMS 01/1368 genotype. At 12 months harvesting period, the garri from NR 07/0240, genotype

was rated best in appearance; 1.02 and 1.30 while garri from TMS070593 was rated least; 3.99 and 3.00 on 5 point hedonic scales (Table 4).

Table 4 Garri appearance as influenced by cassava genotype at different time of harvesting

Cassava genotypes	2012/2013				2013/2014			
	Months after planting				Months after planting			
	8	10	12	Mean	8	10	12	Mean
NR 07/0145	1.94	1.66	1.70	1.77	1.33	1.88	1.40	1.54
NR 07/0246	1.01	1.89	2.80	1.90	1.45	2.01	1.39	1.62
TMS 1070134	2.59	1.63	2.95	2.39	1.00	1.78	1.43	1.40
TMS 01/1412	2.41	2.91	3.18	2.83	1.20	1.99	1.60	1.60
NR 07/0240	1.55	1.08	1.02	1.22	1.10	1.75	1.30	1.38
TMS 1061635	4.14	2.02	4.09	3.42	4.20	3.05	2.90	3.38
TMS 1070337	3.45	2.18	3.92	3.18	1.34	2.45	2.10	1.96
TMS 01/1368	3.91	3.01	2.84	3.25	2.00	3.13	1.80	2.31
TMS 01/1371	2.40	2.84	2.08	2.44	2.90	2.49	2.15	2.52
TMS 070593	4.10	3.55	2.99	3.55	3.95	3.14	3.00	3.36
LSD(p<0.05)	1.93	1.67	1.38	1.21	1.70	1.45	1.56	1.40

Garri texture as influenced by cassava genotypes varied significantly ($p < 0.05$) in all the harvesting period irrespective of cropping season (Table 5). At 8 month, garri from TMS 01/1371 genotype was the finest in texture in both cropping seasons. The least ranked (4.26 and 4.22) at 8 months harvesting in terms of garri texture was TMS1070134. At 10 and 12 months, the garri from TMS 1061635

genotype was rated as the finest (1.01) and (1.50) on 6-point hedonic scale in both cropping season. At 12 months harvesting, it was rated the finest (1.12 and 1.73) in both cropping seasons. The least rated garri in terms of texture at 10 months harvesting (3.80 and 3.34) was from TMS1070134 while it was also rated least in texture (3.75 and 3.79) at 12 months harvesting.

Table 5 Garri texture as influenced by cassava genotypes at different time of harvesting

Cassava genotypes	2012/2013				2013/2014			
	Months after planting				Months after planting			
	8	10	12	Mean	8	10	12	Mean
NR 07/0145	1.84	2.36	1.36	1.85	1.58	2.61	1.36	1.85
NR 07/0246	1.92	1.43	2.25	1.87	2.01	1.98	2.25	1.87
TMS 1070134	4.26	3.80	3.75	3.44	4.22	3.34	3.79	3.94
TMS 01/1412	2.10	1.94	2.81	2.28	2.56	3.09	2.81	2.28
NR 07/0240	1.80	1.90	2.00	1.90	1.90	1.71	1.90	1.90
TMS 1061635	2.32	1.01	1.12	1.48	2.20	1.50	1.12	1.48
TMS 1070337	2.45	3.36	3.68	3.27	1.50	2.13	3.68	3.16
TMS 01/1368	3.42	3.75	3.60	3.59	2.15	2.58	3.60	3.59
TMS 01/1371	1.55	2.61	2.91	2.36	1.65	1.59	1.91	2.36
TMS 070593	2.30	3.14	2.12	2.75	2.10	3.24	2.12	2.52
LSD(p<0.05)	1.77	1.80	1.55	1.23	1.61	1.49	1.82	1.31

Sipping quality as influenced by garri from different cassava genotypes differs significantly ($p<0.05$). In 2012/2013 and 2013/2014, irrespective of time of harvesting, garri from NR07/0240 genotype was rated best as the most preferred for sipping (Table 6). The most dislike garri for sipping at 8 months harvesting was garri from TMS 01/1368 genotype (3.72) and (3.88) on 5-point

hedonic scale in both cropping seasons. At 10 months harvesting, the most dislike garri for sipping in both cropping seasons (3.76 and 3.34) was from TMS1070337. At 12 months harvesting, the most dislike garri sipping (3.53) and (3.98) on 5-point hedonic scale was recorded in garri made from TMS1070337.

Table 6 Sipping quality of garri as influenced by cassava genotypes at different time of harvesting

Cassava genotypes	2012/2013				2013/2014			
	Months after planting				Months after planting			
	8	10	12	Mean	8	10	12	Mean
NR 07/0145	3.10	2.32	1.45	2.29	1.46	1.51	1.45	1.47
NR 07/0246	2.81	1.95	1.78	2.18	2.00	1.76	1.56	1.77
TMS 1070134	3.06	3.01	3.01	3.03	3.22	2.14	2.15	2.50
TMS 01/1412	2.90	1.77	2.23	2.30	2.44	2.29	2.21	2.31
NR 07/0240	1.20	1.43	1.13	1.25	1.30	1.00	1.32	1.21
TMS 1061635	2.33	1.41	1.45	1.73	2.40	1.90	1.45	1.917
TMS 1070337	2.65	3.76	3.53	3.31	2.80	3.34	3.98	3.37
TMS 01/1368	3.72	3.34	3.10	3.39	3.88	2.18	2.10	2.72
TMS 01/1371	1.75	2.36	2.65	2.25	1.64	1.49	1.91	1.68
TMS 070593	2.60	3.12	2.17	2.63	2.34	2.24	2.23	2.27
LSD(p<0.05)	1.11	1.31	1.56	1.50	1.39	0.99	1.09	1.35

Dough quality of *eba* as influenced by cassava genotypes varied significantly among the cassava genotypes in all the harvesting periods irrespective of cropping season (Table 7). NR07/02460 was rated best in making of *eba* at 8 months harvesting; 1.10 and 1.04 in 5 point hedonic scale. The least quality of *eba* at 8 months harvesting 4.70 and 4.19 was recorded in garri prepared from TMS 070593.

At 10 months harvesting. Garri from NR07/0240 was rated best in making *eba*, followed by garri from TMS1070337. The most disliked in making of *eba* was TMS 070593 genotype. At 12 months harvesting, NR07/0240 was the most preferred in *eba* while TMS1070134 was the most disliked at 12 months harvesting.

Table 7: Dough quality of *eba* as influenced by cassava genotypes at different time of harvesting

Cassava genotypes	2012/2013				2013/2014			
	Months after planting				Months after planting			
	8	10	12	Mean	8	10	12	Mean
NR 07/0145	3.41	3.04	3.25	3.23	3.68	1.84	3.11	2.88
NR 07/0246	3.14	3.12	3.11	3.123	2.48	2.11	2.19	2.26
TMS 1070134	2.70	2.84	3.51	3.02	3.11	1.69	3.40	2.73
TMS 01/1412	2.40	2.01	1.18	1.86	2.50	1.33	2.66	2.16
NR 07/0240	1.10	1.44	1.12	1.22	1.04	1.12	1.01	1.06
TMS 1061635	4.01	2.98	3.17	3.39	2.30	1.18	2.40	1.96
TMS 1070337	1.20	1.48	1.14	1.27	1.89	2.16	2.14	2.06
TMS 01/1368	4.10	2.96	2.18	3.08	1.92	2.68	1.10	1.90
TMS 01/1371	4.40	3.77	2.30	3.49	2.30	3.18	1.92	2.47
TMS 070593	4.70	3.99	3.15	3.95	4.19	3.49	2.18	3.29
LSD (p<0.05)	1.38	1.20	1.08	1.18	1.77	1.45	1.50	1.12

Discussion

Result showed significant variations in qualities of garri made from different bio-fortified cassava at different harvesting stage. The same variation also existed in bulking of storage roots. Some cassava genotypes such as (TMS01/1412, NR07/0240 and TMS01/1368) bulked earlier at 8 months

compared to such genotype as NRCOBS3-5-4, NR05/0028 and TMS98/0581 that bulked late but produced significantly higher storage root at 12 MAP. Comparing their yields at all the harvesting periods, cassava storage root yield varied among the genotypes at different harvesting periods. This observation was in-line with the reports of IITA (1990); Nnodu *et al* (2006); Bassey and Harry (2013). IITA

(1990) reported that time to harvest cassava depends on the variety, soil and climatic factors. Nnodu *et al*, (2006) reported that some early cassava variety mature in 7 months after planting (MAP) while some matured at 12 MAP. Ikeh *et al*, (2013); Bassey and Harry (2013) reported differences in maturation of different cassava genotypes. Ikeh *et al*, (2013) reported that cassava varieties such as TMS96/1632, TMS98/2101 and 99/2123 matured early at 9 MAP while some varieties such as 98/0505, 98/0581 and TMS30572 matured at 12 MAP. The result of the study also indicated variations in yield of cassava genotypes at different sampling periods, some matured at 8 months while some matured at 10 and 12 months. The differences observed at 8, 10 and 12 months harvesting periods means that different cassava genotypes have different dry matter partitioning stages; while some partitioned early and some partitioned late. The observation is agrees with the findings of Ikeh (2017) that storage roots of cassava is not only determined by amount of dry matter produced, but also by the pattern of partitioning of the dry matter to different crop during different growth stages.

The differences on appearance, texture, dough quality and other organoleptic qualities of garri recorded in different cassava genotypes

at different time of harvesting may also be attributed to some factors such as inherent characteristics of different genotypes, plant age, and environmental factors. According to Adejumo and Raji (2010), Sanni ((1990), and Karim *et al*. (2009) most of carbohydrate in cassava harvested in the rainy season has been hydrolysed into free sugars

The differences observed in appearance, texture and taste could be due to the fact that variation in genetic make-up of the cassava genotypes. Also, differences in the bulking and maturation period of different biofortified cassava genotypes could have resulted to differences sensory attributes. It had been observed that panelists appreciated garri samples quality based on color or appearance and taste. The result is in agreement with Agbor-Egbe and Mbome (2006), who reported that garri preference was attributed to the better organoleptic characteristics such as appearance, odor, particle size, swelling properties, and eating quality. Similarly, Agbor-Egbe and Mbome (2006) observed that the gari produced from different cassava varieties varies in preference. Ossai *et al*, (2024) in their study reported significant variations in elemental composition of different pro-vitamin A cassava varieties, reflecting slight differences in their genetic makeup.

Conclusion

The result of the study confirmed that bio-fortified cassava genotypes varies in storage root and garri yields as well as sensory properties. Based on the results of the study, the followings were concluded; NR07/0240 showed superiority in storage root and garri yield followed by NR07/0246 and TMS01/1412. Comparing the overall sensory attributes of garri, NR07/0240 was rated best in appearance while TMS 070593 was the least in appearance. TMS 1061635 was the finest in texture while TMS 1070134 was the coarsest. NR07/0240 was best in sipping and dough quality. Therefore, the study recommended those cassava genotypes with superior sensory attributes to cassava processors. The study also suggests more in deep study on organoleptic qualities of other cassava processed products from pro-vitamin A cassava.

Acknowledgment

The authors wish to express our profound gratitude to Prof. N. U. Ndaeyo, Vice Chancellor of University of Uyo, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State for initiating and supervising the study. Special thanks to Prof (Mrs.) Edna A. Akpan, Dean Faculty of Agriculture, Akwa Ibom State University, Obio Akpa Campus, Harvest-Plus Team Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

Also, the contributions of National Root Crop Research Institute (Umudike), Umuahia Abia State and International Institute for Tropical Agriculture (IITA) for provision of pro-vitamin A cassava genotypes and processing centre, is well appreciated. Our special thanks goes to the management of National Cereals Research Institute (NCRI) Uyo out station for provision of land where the experiment was conducted.

References

- Adejumo, B. A and Raji, A. O. (2010) "An appraisal of gari packaging in Ogbomoso, Southwestern Nigeria," *Journal of Agricultural and Veterinary Sciences*, vol. no.2, pp. 120–127.
- Agbor-Egbe, T. and Mbome, I. L. (2006). The effects of processing techniques in reducing cyanogen levels during the production of some Cameroonian cassava foods, *Journal of Food Composition and Analysis*, vol. 19, no. 4, pp. 354–363.
- Akpan, E. A., Ikeh, A. O., Ndaeyo, N. U., Enyong, J. K and Osundare, K. O (2013). Evaluation of Yield and Morphological Characteristics of Casava (*Manihot esculanta Crantz*) Genotype in Uyo, Southeastern Nigerian. In: *Proceedings of First National Conference of the Crop Science Society of Nigeria*. University of Nigeria Nsukka September, 2013. Pp. 150-154.

- Ashoka, P.V., Nair, S.V. and Kurian, T. M.(1984).Influence of Stages of Harvest on the Yield and Quality of Cassava(*Manihot esculenta*). *Madraos Agricultural Journal*, 71:447-449.
- Bassey, E. E. and Harry, G. I. (2013). Screening Cassava (*Manihot esculenta* Crantz) Genotypes for Tuber Bulking, Early maturing and Optimum Harvesting Time in Uyo, South Eastern Nigeria. *Peak Journal of Agricultural Science*,1 (5): 83-88.
- El- Sharkawy, M.A.(2007). Physiological Characteristics of Cassava Tolerance to Prolonged Drought in the Tropics: Implications for Breeding Cultivars Adapted to Seasonally Dry and Semi-Arid Environments. *Brazil Journal of Plant Physiology*, 19:83-98.
- Food and Agriculture Organisation of United Nations (FAO) (2015). Cassava Production and Utilization Statistics www.faostat.foa.org.Cited4 March, 2016.
- Ihekoronye, A.I and Ngoddy,P.O.(1985). *Integrated Food Science and Technology for Tropics*. Macmillian Education Publisher, London, p.386.
- Ikeh, A, O., Ndaeyo, N.U and Ikeh, C.E. (2023). Effects of integrated fertilization on soil sustainability and cassava (*Manihot esculenta* Crantz) yield in an ultisol, *Journal of Current Opinion in Crop Science*, 4(2): 89-102.
- Ikeh, A. O., Essang, D. M., Akata, O. R and Ndaeyo, N. U. (2013). Evaluation of Yield and Yield Components of Cassava (*Manihot esculenta* Crantz) Genotypes at Different Harvesting Stages in Uyo, Southeastern Nigeria. In: *Proceedings of 47th Annual Conference of the Agricultural Society of Nigeria* Held at Federal College of Animal, Health and Production Technology, Moore Plantation, Ibadan. 4th-8th November, 2013, pp. 16-18.
- Ikeh, A.O., Nwanne, A. J and Sampson, H.U (2023). Effects of Planting Population, Planting Position and Number of Nodes per Cutting on Cassava (*Manihot esculenta* Crantz) Seed Yield. *Journal of Agriculture and Forestry Research*, 2:3: 89-97.
- Ikeh,A.O.(2017).Effects of Time of Harvesting and Fertilization on Yield, Garrification Traits and Economic Returns of some Cassava (*Manihot esculenta* Crantz) Genotypes. Unpublished Ph.D Thesis of Department of Crop Science, University of Uyo, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State Nigeria.
- Inacio, K. A. M., Farfan, N. C., Azevedo, C. E. X., Polatto, M. A. G., Carrion, N. S., Mendes, P. V. S. and Santos, E. F. (2024). Potential of Cassava Clones for Iron, Zinc, and Selenium Biofortification. *Agriculture*, 14(2), 268. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture14020268>
- International Institute Tropical Agriculture (IITA, 1990). Cassava in Tropical Africa: A Reference Manual. Chayce

- Publication Services, United Kingdom Edition, p.196.
- Karim, O. R., Fasasi, O. S. and Oyeyinka, S. A. (2009). Gari yield and chemical composition of cassava roots stored using traditional methods, *Pakistan Journal of Nutrition*, vol. 8, no. 12, pp. 1830– 1833.
- Lucia, M.J.C, Alcide, R.G.O, Ronoel L.O.G, Sidney, P. Marilia, R.N; Jose L.V.C, Elenilda, J.P; and Wania, G. F. (2012). Retention of total carotenoid and β -carotene in yellow sweet cassava (*Manihot esculenta* Crantz) after domestic cooking. *Journal of Nutritional Research* 56 (10) 34-40.
- Maziya-Dixon, B., Akinyele,I.O., Oguntona, E.B., Nokoe, Sanusi, R.A and Harris,E. (2004). Nigeria Food Consumption and Nutrition Survey. *2001-2003 Summary Report of International Institute of Tropical Agriculture Ibadan, Nigeria*, pp. 67.
- Ngendahayo,M. and Dixon, A.G.O. (2001).Effect of Varying Stages of Harvest on Tuber Yield, Dry Matter, Starch and Harvest Index of Cassava in Two Ecological Zones of Nigeria. In: *Proceedings of the 7th Triennial Symposium of the International Society of for Tropical Root Crops-African Branch Held in 11-17 October,1998 at Centre international des Conferences, Cotonou, Benin*, pp. 661-666.
- Nnodu, E. O. Ezulike, T. O. and Asumugha, G.N. (2006). Cassava. In: N. U. A Idem and Showeminio, F. A. (eds). *Tuber and Fibre Crops of Nigeria. Principles of Production and Utilization*, Zaria, Kaduna, Ade Commercial Press Publisher, pp. 22-44.
- Onwueme, I.C., and Sinha, T.D. (1991). *Field Crop Production in Tropical Africa*. CTA, Ede Publishers, Netherlands.p.480.
- Ossai, F. K., Peretomode O. V., Ossai, C.O.,Akpeji, S. C. (2024). Assessment of levels of selected macro and microelements present in biofortified provitamin-A cassava varieties. *Journal of Current Opinion in Crop Science*, 5(1), 21-26. <https://doi.org/10.62773/jcocs.v5i1.224>
- Peters, S. W., USoro, E. J., Udo, E. J., Obot, U. W. and Okpon, S. N. (eds), (1989). *Akwa Ibom State: Physical Background, Soils and Land use and ecological problems. a technical report of the task force on soils and land use survey, Akwa Ibom State*. 603p.
- Sanni, L. O. (1990) “Hazard analysis of critical control points in the commercial production of high quality gari,” *Nigeria Journal of Science*, vol. 24.

UCCDA (1989). Year Report. Uyo Capital
City Development Authority.
UyoAkwa Ibom State.